

PROBABILISTIC STRENGTH ESTIMATION IN CONSIDERATION OF SIZE EFFECTS AND LOAD MODES FOR GLASS-SHORT-FIBRE- REINFORCED THERMOSETTING PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Three kinds of basic strength tests were conducted at room temperature to develop a strength prediction method for glass-short-fibre-reinforced thermosetting plastics with various volume fibre fractions. We chose glass-short-fibre-reinforced phenolic resin composites (GSP) as a test material and obtained the Weibull coefficients for the GSP strength by using the Weibull statistical theory. Relationships between the GSP strength and effective volume calculated by using material mechanics agreed with the effective volume theory equation on a double logarithmic chart. We carried out a tensile test with open-hole (OH) specimens to verify whether the technique developed in this study can estimate the strength of an actual shape. The effective volume of the specimens was calculated by integrating the maximum principal stress distribution, which was obtained by finite element analysis (FEA), with the volume. Fracture probability distributions predicted by using the Weibull theory were applicable to the strength evaluation of GSP. We acquired maximum errors by comparing the results of both the FEA and an experiment and then determined that the error met our target value by data validation. This prediction method has the potential to reduce the number of trials and development cost.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short fibre reinforced plastic (SFRP) is used increasingly as a structure material because of its superior mechanical and lightweight properties. However, SFRP fractures generally show complex behaviour with combined matrix cracks, broken fibres, fibre pull-out, and others. Therefore, predicting the strength properties of SFRP is difficult. To assure the safety of SFRP products, we have needed to repeat test productions. Reducing the number of test productions is directly linked to decreasing the cost of development. We should develop high-reliability strength evaluation techniques to meet the increase in products that will use SFRP in the future. Research papers on the strength properties of SFRP in relation to the prediction of static strength and elastic modulus have been reported. Further, the strength properties of SFRP obtained by test specimens of different sizes organized by Weibull distribution are discussed by Hashemi et al. [1] and A. S. D. Wang et al. [2]. Thus, the effective volume theory based on the Weibull theory can be applied to SFRP [3] in consideration of test piece level. Although the effects are known, reports of such application to an actual structure are not found. This is because a design approach that takes into account the effect of size has not been established. Therefore, we thought that we can predict strength by applying an effective volume theory in consideration of structure shape, stress distribution, and Weibull parameters. The main purpose of this

work is to establish a strength prediction method for SFRP by using experiments and finite element analysis simulation.

In this paper, we cover glass-short-fibre-reinforced phenolic resin composites (GSP) having excellent strength properties and heat resistance. To investigate the strength of GSP in comparison with various volume fibre fractions V_f (0%, 20%, and 50%), three kinds of basic strength tests (3-point bending, 4-point bending, and tensile) were carried out at room temperature. To verify the efficiency of the effective volume theory, open-hole-specimens (OH specimens) made of GSP were subjected to tensile tests. The effective volume of the specimens was calculated by integrating the stress distribution, which was obtained by finite element analysis, with the volume. Then, the distribution of fracture probabilities was predicted by using the Weibull statistical theory, which is applicable to evaluating the strength of GSP.

2 DETAILS OF STATIC TEST PROCEDURE

2.1 Material constitutions

Table 1 lists the configuration of the GSP [4]. For the test specimens, we fabricated 300-mm-square and 30-mm-thick bulk plates of GSP with various fibre volume fractions V_f (0%, 20%, and 50%) by using the compression moulding process. Thermosetting phenolic resin was used as the matrix resin. The reinforcement was a short glass fibre 10 mm long and with a diameter of 10 micrometres. As for the moulding condition, the mould temperature was 160°C, the press pressure was 20 MPa, and the curing time was 250 seconds. To determine the distribution of fibre in GSP, as shown in Fig. 1, we polished the GSP specimens in the thickness direction and observed the polished surfaces with scanning electron microscopy.

Table 1 Configuration of GSP materials [4]

Component		0.0 V_f	0.2 V_f	0.5 V_f
Glass fibre	[%]	0	20	50
Phenolic resin	[%]	70 ~ 85	55 ~ 65	30 ~ 35
Phenol	[%]	1	←	←
Hexamethylene tetramine	[%]	3	←	←
Rock wool	[%]	10 ~ 20	←	←
Zinc stearate	[%]	1.0 ~ 2.0	←	←

Fig. 1 Observing glass short fibre distribution

2.2 Static test method and strain measurement

In this study, we conducted multiple strength tests (3-point bending, 4-point bending, and tensile) to obtain strengths in different loading modes at room temperature. All the tests were performed by using a testing machine that combined tension/torsion electro-hydraulic servo systems under axial-

loads up to ± 25 kN with standard displacements of ± 50 mm and torsion-torques up to 220 N·m with total rotations of 270°.

Each specimen was cut from the fabricated bulk materials as described in section 2.1. Bending test specimens 50 mm in length, 10 mm in width, and 5 mm in thickness were used as shown in Fig. 2 at a cross-head displacement rate of 0.1 mm/sec. The 3-point bending (3PB) and 4-point bending (4PB) tests were performed in an outer span length L_2 , which is shown in Fig. 2. The tension tests were performed by using a round-bar specimen with the dimensions shown in Fig. 3. We measured the loading force and displacement of all specimens. Some of the test pieces were placed under longitudinal strain by using a contact measurement method, i.e., strain gauges or extensometers, during material tests. After that, we obtained stress-strain curves to determine elastic modules.

To verify the availability of the effective volume theory proposed in this paper, the open-hole specimen shown in Fig. 4 was subjected to a tensile test. For digital image correlation (DIC) system measurement, a mottled black and white pattern was made on the OH specimen surfaces. Moreover, we also applied strain gauges (gauge length: 2 mm) on the OH specimen to validate the DIC measurement. Figure 5 shows the experimental set-up used in the OH specimen test. This set-up consists of a material testing machine and the DIC systems.

Fig. 2 Bending test set up

Fig. 3 Tensile test set up

Fig. 4 Open-hole (OH) specimen with strain gauges and random patterns

Fig. 5 DIC measurement systems with material test machines

3 STATIC STRENGTH TEST RESULTS

3.1 Strength test results

Table 2 shows the static strength test results. We compared the test results with the same V_f with respect to each load mode. In the case of the uniaxial loading mode in this study, the static strength increased in the order of the tensile strength, 4PB, and 3PB. The GSP showed that all had different strengths in the results of 3PB tests, 4PB tests, and tensile tests.

These results imply that we cannot uniquely determine the material strength of the GSP without dependence on the specimen size. These results also suggested that the SGP has a size effect independent of the loading mode. Moreover, all of the specimens underwent brittle failure without dependence on loading modes. Every GSP fracture surface indicated brittleness, and we observed that cracks propagated perpendicularly in the maximum principal stress direction. Such materials are well known as being in accordance with Weibull distribution.

Table 2 List of static test results in GSP

Loading mode	V_f [-]	Number of samples	σ_{ave} [N/mm ²]	σ_{min} [N/mm ²]	σ_{max} [N/mm ²]
3-point bending	0.0	20	80.5	64.4	91.5
	0.2	20	88.7	78.1	100.9
	0.5	20	128.1	107.8	140.0
4-point bending	0.0	15	73.0	60.8	81.3
	0.2	14	84.7	75.0	98.2
	0.5	15	116.3	103.7	132.7
Tensile	0.0	5	37.6	28.6	45.4
	0.2	6	45.1	39.1	54.5
	0.5	5	60.5	53.6	69.7

3.2 Weibull statistical analysis for GSP strength

We organized strengths with a two-parameter Weibull distribution [1-3]. Strengths were obtained with each static test, which was expressed with the two-parameter Weibull distribution given by equation (1), where σ is the stress that occurred in the specimens, σ_0 is the scale parameter, and m is the shape parameter, which is generally referred to as the Weibull parameter.

$$P = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (1)$$

$$P = \frac{i - 0.3}{n + 0.4} \quad (2)$$

A fracture probability P corresponding to arbitrary σ_f was assigned by using the median rank method given by equation (2), where n is the number of samples, i is cumulative of the number of tests.

Weibull plots for the GSP strength are shown in Fig. 6. We observed that the Weibull charts for the GSP strength against the fracture probability were linearly plotted without dependence on the loading mode. However, as shown in Table 3, in the comparison with m in each loading mode, the Weibull parameters were approximately divided into various ranges; the tensile tests were from 5.8 to 10.2, and the flexural tests were from 13.5 to 17.6. The Weibull parameter widely varied depending on the loading mode. Therefore, it is suggested that the fracture strength and its variability depend on the loading modes and specimen sizes as well as V_f .

Fig. 6 Weibull distribution of fracture strength

Table 3 Weibull coefficients of GSP for various specimen sizes

Loading mode	V_f [-]	m	σ_0 [N/mm ²]
3-point bending	0.0	13.5	83.6
	0.2	16.1	91.5
	0.5	17.5	131.9
4-point bending	0.0	14.1	75.6
	0.2	15.7	85.9
	0.5	17.6	119.7
Tensile	0.0	5.8	40.4
	0.2	8.1	46.8
	0.5	10.2	63.2

3.3 Applying the effective volume theory to GSP strength

As discussed in section 3.1, the GSP showed that all had different strengths in the results of the static test series. If such a dependence of size on the strength is to be in accordance with the effective volume theory, we assumed that we would be capable of obtaining a strength criterion in consideration of structure shape, scale, and stress distribution. We therefore organized the test results by applying the effective volume theory based on the Weibull statistical theory and tried to obtain equivalency between various test conditions.

A two-parameter Weibull probability distribution P in the stress distribution on an arbitrary

volume is given by equation (3), where σ is the actual stress, σ_0 is the scale parameter, V_0 is the criterion volume, and m is the shape parameter. The strength ratio of σ_1 and σ_2 is expressed by the m -th power ratio of arbitrary effective volume $V_{\text{eff}1}$ and $V_{\text{eff}2}$ as equation (4).

$$P=1-\exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m \frac{V}{V_0}\right] \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1}=\left(\frac{V_{\text{eff}1}}{V_{\text{eff}2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (4)$$

According to the effective volume theory given as equation (4), if σ_0 and m in the arbitrary volume are obtained, we are able to estimate the GSP strength in the effective volume V_{eff} . V_0 was assumed to be 1-mm^3 in this discussion, and each \hat{m}_0 and $\hat{\sigma}_0$, which are indicated as the estimation value of m_0 and σ_0 , was obtained by statistical analysis. When the each estimation value is substituted with equation (4), the relationships between the SGP strength σ_f and the arbitrary effective volume V_{eff} can be expressed with equation (5).

$$\sigma_f=\hat{\sigma}_0\left(\frac{1}{V_{\text{eff}}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\hat{m}_0}} \quad (5)$$

The effective volumes of specimens for bending and tensile strength can be calculated on the basis of material mechanics. The effective volume V_{eff} was individually calculated by measuring the dimension to an accuracy of 0.01 mm because each specimen had a machining error.

Figure 7 shows the relationships between σ_f and V_{eff} depending on the fibre volume fraction V_f on a double-logarithmic chart. A solid line represents GSP strength estimation curves based on the effective volume theory equation. The curves are in good agreement with the experimental results.

The V_{eff} of a simple shape specimen can be calculated with a material mechanics theory by using \hat{m}_0 . This parameter has to be estimated to express the relationships between the strength and the effective volume with a single curve as below. We calculated the effective volume with a temporary shape parameter m_0 . Then, a fitting curve, which has a slope of m_0 on a double-logarithmic chart, was obtained that showed the relationships between σ_f and V_{eff} . Finally, an iterative calculation was carried out until the temporary \hat{m}_0 agreed with the inverse value of the fitted curve slope m_0 . The determined Weibull parameters are also shown in Fig. 7. These parameters are taken as the inherent Weibull parameters in consideration of the specimen shape and load mode in this study. This result suggests that the effective volume theory can be used to predict the uniaxial fracture strength of the GSP.

Fig. 7 Relationships between strength and effective volume

4 PROBABILISTIC ESTIMATION IN GSP STATIC STRENGTH

4.1 Finite element analysis in OH specimens

We verified the availability of the proposed estimation method based on the Weibull statistical theory by applying a finite element analysis (FEA) and strength test to the OH specimen.

A typical FE mesh is shown in Fig. 10. To simplify the FE model, the part held by the hydraulic grip region is omitted. In consideration of the symmetrical shape of a specimen, we create a one-eighth symmetry FE mesh generated by a single three dimensional solid element. The OH specimen FE model contained 7,868 nodes and 6,012 elements. Symmetric constraint conditions on the x , y , and z directions are applied to each cut boundary surface. The uniform tensile force F applied to the edge surface is increased step-by-step in 20 increments. Then, the principal stress and an individual element volume that corresponds to each step is outputted. Elastic modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν used as the material properties for the FE model are shown in Table 4.

Fig. 8 Finite element model for OH specimen (one-eighth symmetrical model)

Table 4 Material properties for FE model of OH specimens

V_f	E [N/mm ²]	ν
0.0	7,140	0.27
0.2	11,800	0.20
0.5	13,100	0.22

4.2 Experiment validation of FE model

We performed an FE analysis (FEA) result validation by using both digital image correlations (DIC) and strain gauge measurements. Figure 9 shows typical comparison images of the results of the FEA and DIC strain measurements. The strain distribution for FEA was equivalent to the DIC measurements, and the strain concentration rate at the hole edge was about 2.4.

Then, the typical stress-strain curves of the OH specimens are shown in Fig. 10. The vertical axis is the nominal stress σ calculated by using the force F by dividing the nominal cross section ($25 \times t_5$), and the horizontal axis is the strain in the y -direction. Strain distribution images taken with DIC are also shown above the stress-strain curve corresponding to the nominal stress history. The strain distribution was higher and higher as σ increased. The stress-strain curve obtained by FEA also matched without dependence on the measurement method and measurement place.

Additionally, all OH specimens were promptly cracked from the hole edge after reaching the maximum σ without dependence on the V_f . A typical fracture situation is shown on the right side of the DIC image in Fig. 10. The crack propagated perpendicularly in the loading direction. The fracture spots did not focus at a particular hole edge. Therefore, the specimens indicated brittleness the same as the basic test pieces as described in section 3.1.

For the elastic stress analysis, the FE analytical results agreed with both of the experimental strain measurements. In accordance with the comparisons stated above, the proposed FEA model is capable of reproducing the experimental results.

Strain distribution diagrams mirrored at C/L

Fig. 9 Comparison of strain distributions with FEA and DIC measurements

Fig. 10 FE analysis and strain measurement assessment with typical stress-strain curves with OH specimen ($0.2 V_f$)

4.3 Considering of strength evaluations in deterministic way

The OH specimen fracture strengths were obtained with the 2.4 stress concentration factor at the hole edge. Table 5 lists the average fracture strength for each specimen. We determined that the maximum stress in OH specimens conformed to none of the specimens. Comparing the OH specimens

with the other specimens, the minimum difference in each V_f was 28.9% ($0.0 V_f$), 17.5% ($0.2 V_f$), and 13.3% ($0.5 V_f$). Therefore, we cannot uniquely determine the GSP fracture strength. This fact suggests the possibility that the GSP strength is disproportionately evaluated on the safe-side or non safe-side.

Table 5 Average fracture strength for each specimen

Test method		$0.0 V_f$	$0.2 V_f$	$0.5 V_f$
3-point bending	[N/mm ²]	80.5	88.7	128.1
4-point bending	[N/mm ²]	73.0	84.7	116.3
Tensile	[N/mm ²]	37.6	45.1	60.5
OH specimen	[N/mm ²]	51.9	69.9	100.8
Minimum error	[%]	28.9	17.5	13.3

4.4 Effective volume calculation using FEA

In this section, we obtain the effective volume V_{eff} by using the FE analytical stress distribution in order to apply the effective volume theory to the OH specimens. In a discretized structure that contains an n element, the V_{eff} of the arbitrary shape structure is calculated by using equation (6), where $\sigma_{p1, \text{max}}$ is the maximum value of the maximum principal stress, \hat{m}_0 is the estimated shape parameter, ΔV_i is a volume in a finite element, and $\sigma_{p1, i}$, $\sigma_{p2, i}$, and $\sigma_{p3, i}$ are the principal stress components [5]. The V_{eff} of the OH specimen with stress distributions applied that was obtained in section 4.2 by using equation (6) is arranged in Table 6.

$$V_{\text{eff}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ \left(\frac{\chi \sigma_{p1, i}}{\sigma_{p1, \text{max}}} \right)^{\hat{m}_0} + \left(\frac{\chi \sigma_{p2, i}}{\sigma_{p1, \text{max}}} \right)^{\hat{m}_0} + \left(\frac{\chi \sigma_{p3, i}}{\sigma_{p1, \text{max}}} \right)^{\hat{m}_0} \right\} \Delta V_i \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \chi &= 1 \text{ as } \sigma_{p1, i}, \sigma_{p2, i}, \sigma_{p3, i} \geq 0 \\ \chi &= 0 \text{ as } \sigma_{p1, i}, \sigma_{p2, i}, \sigma_{p3, i} < 0 \end{aligned}$$

Table 6 Effective volumes of OH specimens

V_f	V_{eff} [mm ³]
0.0	47.7
0.2	22.1
0.5	41.1

$$P = 1 - \exp \left[- \left\{ \left(\frac{\sigma_{p1, \text{max}}}{\hat{\sigma}_0} \right)^{\hat{m}_0} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{p2, \text{max}}}{\hat{\sigma}_0} \right)^{\hat{m}_0} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{p3, \text{max}}}{\hat{\sigma}_0} \right)^{\hat{m}_0} \right\} V_{\text{eff}} \right] \quad (7)$$

Multi-axial stress states generally occur in a loaded actual structure. Therefore, when fracture promptly occurs, the fracture probability P is rewritten by extending equation (3) with $\sigma_{p1, i}$, $\sigma_{p2, i}$, and $\sigma_{p3, i}$ and $\sigma_{p1, \text{max}}$, $\sigma_{p2, \text{max}}$, and $\sigma_{p3, \text{max}}$ as the maximum value of principal stress components. Here, equation (6) is inserted into equation (7) as V_{eff} . By applying the Weibull parameters in Fig. 7 and the maximum value of maximum principal stresses $\sigma_{p1, \text{max}(k)}$ coinciding with the uniform tensile force F_k ($k=1, \dots, k$) in each step, we can obtain the fracture probability P_k corresponding to F_k . The strength of the GSP structure can be predicted by calculating the fracture probability distribution with the FE analytical stress distribution as stated above.

4.5 Probabilistic estimation in OH specimen strength

The fracture probability distribution in the OH specimens is shown in Fig. 11, which shows the relationships between the fracture probability P and tensile force F for each V_f . The plot in Fig. 11 indicates the tensile test results for the OH specimens assigned with the median rank method.

The difference between the experimental fracture forces and analytical predicted values for the average ($P = 0.5$ in Fig. 11) is as follows. $0.0V_f$ is 2.87 kN and 3.01 kN (error of 4.7%), $0.2V_f$ is 3.84 kN and 4.05 kN (error of 5.2%), and $0.5 V_f$ is 5.53 kN and 5.39 kN (error of 2.6%).

As explained above, we confirmed that the proposed method has the potential to predict the GSP fracture strength without relying on the V_f in less than 5% of errors. Therefore, this method has the potential to reduce the number of trials and the development cost.

The GSP strength is likely to be dominated by manufacturing defects during the moulding process [6]. As future work, we will investigate the effects of moulding processes and defect sizes to improve the accuracy of the proposed method.

Fig.11 Relationships between fracture probabilities and forces for each V_f

5 CONCLUSIONS

We investigated the fibre volume fraction (V_f) dependence on the strength of glass-short-fibre-reinforced phenolic resin plastics (GSP) made by press moulding. Three kinds of basic strength tests (3-point bending, 4-point bending, and tensile) were conducted at room temperature to investigate the GSP strength in comparison with various volume fibre V_f (0%, 20%, and 50%). The obtained strength data were analysed by using the Weibull statistical theory. Then, open-hole specimens (OH specimens) made of GSP were subjected to tensile tests to verify the efficiency of the effective volume theory. The conclusions of the present study are as below.

- (1) The static strength increased in the order of the tensile strength, 4PB, and 3PB. The GSP showed that all had different strengths in the results of the 3PB, 4PB, and tensile tests.
- (2) We confirmed that the Weibull charts in the GSP strength against the fracture probability were linearly plotted without dependence on the loading mode. The Weibull shape parameter ranged from 5.8 to 17.6. It is suggested that the fracture strength and its variability depend on loading modes and specimen sizes as well as V_f .
- (3) The relationships between σ_f and V_{eff} in consideration of the fibre volume fraction V_f agreed well with the experiment results on the double-logarithmic chart.
- (4) We performed an FEA result validation by using both digital image correlations (DIC) and contact strain measurements. The strain distribution was higher and higher as σ increased. The stress-strain curve obtained by FEA also matched without dependence on the measurement method and measurement place in accordance with the typical stress-strain curves of the OH specimens. The proposed FEA model is capable of reproducing the experimental results.

- (5) As shown by relationships between the fracture probability P and tensile force F in each V_f , the difference between experimental fracture forces, and the analytical predicted values in the average ($P = 0.5$), we confirmed that the proposed method has the potential to predict the GSP fracture strength without relying on the V_f in less than 5% of errors.

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